

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE VIRAL HEPATITIS IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN**Sharibaev I.T.¹, Zhanibekov Zh.Zh.¹, Mukhammadieva M.I.²**¹Karakalpakstan Medical Institute, Nukus, Karakalpakstan, Uzbekistan²Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Resume. Acute viral hepatitis remains one of the most significant infectious diseases affecting global public health. The Republic of Karakalpakstan, located in the northern region of Uzbekistan, is characterized by specific epidemiological conditions that contribute to the spread of viral hepatitis. This study aimed to investigate the clinical and laboratory characteristics of acute viral hepatitis in patients treated in infectious diseases hospitals of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The research included patients diagnosed with acute viral hepatitis who underwent comprehensive clinical and laboratory examination. The results showed that intoxication syndrome, jaundice, and dyspeptic disorders were the most common clinical manifestations. Laboratory findings revealed elevated bilirubin levels and increased activity of liver transaminases (ALT and AST), which serve as important diagnostic indicators. Early diagnosis and timely treatment play a crucial role in preventing complications and improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: acute viral hepatitis, clinical manifestations, laboratory indicators, Karakalpakstan, infectious diseases.

ҚОРАҚАЛПОҒИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА ЎТКИР ВИРУСЛИ ГЕПАТИТЛАРНИНГ КЛИНИКО-ЛАБОРАТОРИЯВИЙ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ**Шарибаев И.Т.¹, Жанибеков Ж.Ж.¹, Мухаммадиева М.И.²**¹Қорақалпоғистон тиббиёт институти, Нукус ш., Қорақалпоғистон, Ўзбекистон²Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Ўткир вирусли гепатитлар бугунги кунда жаҳон миқёсида жамоат саломатлиги учун энг муҳим юқумли касалликлардан бири ҳисобланади. Ўзбекистоннинг шимолий ҳудудида жойлашган Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси вирусли гепатитлар тарқалишига таъсир кўрсатувчи ўзига хос эпидемиологик шароитлар билан тавсифланади. Ушбу тадқиқотнинг мақсади Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси инфекция касалликлар шифохоналарида даволанган беморларда ўткир вирусли гепатитларнинг клиник ва лабораториявий хусусиятларини ўрганишдан иборат бўлди. Тадқиқотга ўткир вирусли гепатит таъхиси қўйилган беморлар жалб этилди ва уларда комплекс клиник ҳамда лаборатория текширувлари ўтказилди. Олинган натижаларга кўра, интоксикация синдроми, сариқлик ва диспептик бузилишлар касалликнинг энг кўп учрайдиган клиник белгилари ҳисобланади. Лаборатория текширувлари натижасида қонда билирубин миқдорининг ошиши ва жигар трансаминазлари (АЛТ ва АСТ) фаоллигининг кўтарилиши аниқланди, бу эса муҳим диагностик кўрсаткичлардан ҳисобланади. Касалликни эрта таъхислаш ва ўз вақтида даволаш асоратларнинг олдини олиш ҳамда даволаш натижаларини яхшилашда муҳим аҳамиятга эга.

Калит сўзлар: ўткир вирусли гепатит, клиник белгилари, лаборатория кўрсаткичлари, Қорақалпоғистон, юқумли касалликлар.

КЛИНИКО-ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОСТРОГО ВИРУСНОГО ГЕПАТИТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН**Шарибаев И.Т.¹, Жанибеков Ж.Ж.¹, Мухаммадиева М.И.²**¹Каракалпакский медицинский институт, г. Нукус, Каракалпакстан, Узбекистан²Бухарский государственный медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино, г. Бухара, Узбекистан

Резюме. Острые вирусные гепатиты остаются одной из наиболее значимых инфекционных проблем общественного здравоохранения во всём мире. Республика Каракалпакстан, расположенная в северном регионе Узбекистана, характеризуется специфическими эпидемиологическими условиями, способствующими распространению вирусных гепатитов. Целью данного исследования было изучение клинико-лабораторных особенностей острого вирусного гепатита у пациентов, проходивших лечение в инфекционных больницах Республики Каракалпакстан. В исследование были включены пациенты с диагнозом острого вирусного гепатита, которым было проведено комплексное клинико-лабораторное обследование. Результаты показали, что наиболее частыми клиническими проявлениями

ями заболевания являются интоксикационный синдром, желтуха и диспепсические расстройства. Лабораторные исследования выявили повышение уровня билирубина и увеличение активности печёночных трансаминаз (АЛТ и АСТ), которые являются важными диагностическими показателями. Ранняя диагностика и своевременное лечение играют ключевую роль в предупреждении осложнений и улучшении исходов заболевания.

Ключевые слова: острый вирусный гепатит, клинические проявления, лабораторные показатели, Каракалпакстан, инфекционные заболевания.

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Relevance of the topic. Viral hepatitis continues to be a major global health problem. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), millions of people are infected with hepatitis viruses every year, and many of them develop severe complications, including chronic liver disease, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma. Acute viral hepatitis (AVH) is an inflammatory disease of the liver caused by hepatotropic viruses, including hepatitis A, B, C, D, and E [1,2].

These infections differ in transmission routes, epidemiological features, and clinical course. Hepatitis A and E are primarily transmitted through the fecal–oral route, whereas hepatitis B, C, and D are transmitted through parenteral exposure, including blood transfusion, medical procedures, and other forms of contact with infected biological fluids [3].

The Republic of Karakalpakstan is considered an epidemiologically important region due to environmental and socio-economic factors [4-6]. The Aral Sea ecological crisis, limited access to clean water resources, and insufficient sanitary conditions create favorable circumstances for the spread of infectious diseases, including viral hepatitis. Therefore, studying the clinical and laboratory features of acute viral hepatitis in this region is important for improving diagnosis and treatment strategies.

Currently, viral hepatitis remains one of the most serious problems of the global healthcare system. The northern region of Uzbekistan, particularly the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is considered a specific epidemiological zone. In this region, both fecal–oral (A, E) and parenteral (B, C, D) transmission routes of viral hepatitis show relatively high prevalence [7]. The scarcity of water resources in the Aral Sea region and the complexity of sanitary and hygienic conditions contribute to the widespread transmission of infection.

Acute viral hepatitis (AVH) is an inflammatory disease of the liver caused by viruses and remains an important medical problem worldwide [8]. According to the World Health Organization, millions of people are infected with viral hepatitis each year, and a certain proportion of them develop severe complications.

Acute viral hepatitis is mainly caused by hepatitis A, B, C, D, and E viruses. These diseases differ in their clinical course, transmission mechanisms, and laboratory parameters. In particular, hepatitis A and E are transmitted mainly through the fecal–oral route, while hepatitis B, C, and D are transmitted through the parenteral route [9].

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, viral hepatitis remains an important epidemiological issue. Therefore, studying the clinical and laboratory characteristics of the disease in this region is of great significance [10].

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted among patients treated in infectious diseases hospitals in the Republic of Karakalpakstan under inpatient conditions. Patients diagnosed with acute viral hepatitis were included in the study, and their clinical and laboratory parameters were comprehensively analyzed. The general clinical condition of patients, disease symptoms, and features of disease progression were assessed. In addition, biochemical blood tests were performed in all patients to evaluate the main laboratory indicators reflecting liver function. Serological and immunological examinations were also carried out to identify the type of viral hepatitis and determine the etiology of the disease. Furthermore, ultrasound diagnostics were used to assess the condition of the liver and other internal organs. Laboratory analysis included the determination of bilirubin levels, ALT and AST enzyme activity, thymol test, and other biochemical indicators characterizing liver function. These examinations played an important role in identifying the clinical course of the disease, structural changes in liver tissue, and pathological processes.

Results. The results showed that acute viral hepatitis in the Republic of Karakalpakstan clinically manifests with intoxication and jaundice syndromes. Laboratory tests revealed that an increase in transaminase activity and elevated bilirubin levels are the main diagnostic criteria.

These findings are consistent with the results of other studies. In addition, early diagnosis and timely treatment play an important role in preventing disease complications.

The results of the study demonstrated that acute viral hepatitis in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is characterized by a combination of clinical and laboratory manifestations typical for inflammatory liver disease.

The most common clinical symptoms observed in patients included general weakness, fatigue, decreased appetite, nausea, vomiting, and pain in the right upper quadrant of the abdomen. Jaundice was one of the main clinical manifestations and was frequently accompanied by dark urine and discoloration of stool. Hepatomegaly was also detected in a significant proportion of patients.

Laboratory findings revealed significant biochemical abnormalities. Elevated levels of total bilirubin were observed in most patients, indicating impaired liver function. Additionally, increased activity of liver enzymes, particularly ALT and AST, was detected, reflecting hepatocellular damage.

The thymol turbidity test was also elevated in many patients, suggesting disturbances in protein metabolism associated with liver dysfunction. These laboratory changes correlated with the clinical severity of the disease.

Conclusion. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, acute viral hepatitis is clinically characterized by intoxication syndrome, jaundice, and dyspeptic disorders. Laboratory findings such as increased bilirubin levels and elevated transaminase activity are considered the main diagnostic indicators. Early diagnosis and effective treatment are important for reducing complications of the disease.

Acute viral hepatitis in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is clinically characterized by intoxication syndrome, jaundice, and dyspeptic disorders. Laboratory findings, including elevated bilirubin levels and increased transaminase activity, serve as key diagnostic indicators of the disease.

Early diagnosis, appropriate laboratory testing, and timely treatment are essential for preventing complications and improving clinical outcomes. Strengthening epidemiological surveillance and preventive measures is also important for reducing the spread of viral hepatitis in the region.

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